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Libre Open Access in Science Journals: An Analytical Study of DOAJ

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Abstract

This study is based on metadata extracted from the well known and authoritative global Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), a database of fully open access peer-reviewed scholarly journals managed by Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA), United Kingdom. Disciplines chosen for the quantitative study belong to Science as categorised in DOAJ were analysed using different criteria like language, Creative Commons (CC) licence, publisher country, etc.,. Findings of the study reveal that there are 104 Zoology Journals, 218 Chemistry Journals, 111 Botany Journals, 139 Geology Journals, 242 Physics Journals, 85 Microbiology Journals, 38 Astronomy Journals, 52 Physiology Journals, 11 Anatomy Journals and 544 Mathematics Journals indexed in DOAJ published from 82 countries in 32 languages. English emerged as the dominant language of publication with 1355 Journals publishing primarily in this language. On the basis of the total journals published in DOAJ of select Journals of Science United Kingdom is ranked 1st with 248 Journals followed by Indonesia (164). The study revealed that 21 Indian Science Journals meet the DOAJ inclusion criteria for indexing. Maximum number of Journals used CC-BY licencing i.e., 830. The study has also found that 2020 can be marked as the most significant year as the highest number of (220) Journals have been added in DOAJ. Most of the Journals do not charge Article Processing Charge (APC) and most of the Journals do not fulfil the guidelines for DOAJ Seal. The paper also highlights the peer review process adopted by the DOAJ Science journals.

Keywords: Open Access, Gratis OA, Libre OA, DOAJ, Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy, Mathematics, Creative Commons.

1. Introduction:

The DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) was launched in 2003 with 300 open access journals covering all areas of science, technology, medicine, social sciences, arts and humanities (Kumar 2018,174-179). Open access journals from all countries and in all languages are welcome to apply for inclusion. DOAJ is funded by several libraries, publishers and other similar organisations. Supporting DOAJ demonstrates a firm commitment to open access and the infrastructure that supports it. As of January 2021, DOAJ contains 5,506,266 articles from 15,671 journals in 80 languages originating from 123 countries. DOAJ spans peer-reviewed scholarly OA journals from STEM as-well-as AHSS. DOAJ is supported by more than 100 voluntary editorial staff who help us review applications for journals to be indexed. All volunteers abide by an agreement without any conflicts of interest. For DOAJ, open access is only when digital content is freely available online and user rights and the terms of copyright are defined.

Open Access (OA) publications can be broadly categorised into Gratis OA and Libre OA, which determines how the publication be used by the end users. Gratis OA means that a publication be viewed and printed at no cost, while Libre OA allows wider use by using Creative Commons

licenses. DOAJ works on the principle that for open access to work effectively, user rights, through licencing, and copyright ownership need to be clear. For this reason, DOAJ only accepts journals that operate a form of Libre Open Access.

Figure 1. Current Status of APC in DOAJ

According to figure above, 73% of the DOAJ journals do not impose APC, whereas for 27% of the OA journals it is mandatory for the authors to pay the APC. It may be articulated here that APC levied by the publisher acts as a hindrance or bottleneck for authors, particularly those from developing economies and with no organisational support in the form of funding.

2. Study Objectives:

This study seeks to assess the status of Science journals of disciplines including Zoology (ZOO), Chemistry (CHEM), Botany (BOT), Geology (GEO), Physics (PHYS), Microbiology (MICRO), Astronomy (ASTR), Physiology (PHYLS), Anatomy (ANAT) and Mathematics (MATH) with reference to various parameters as mentioned here. The study objectives are to:

- i. Ascertain the number of Science journals and their respective countries indexed in DOAJ.
- ii. Determine the correlation (if any) between the journals and articles.
- iii. Know the adoption of open access by the Indian Journals in DOAJ.
- iv. Identify the language coverage of science journals.
- v. Highlight APC charges/handling fees of Science Journals.
- vi. Analyse the status of open licence adopted by Science Journals.
- vii. Assess the year-by-year inclusion of Science Journals in DOAJ.

3. Methodology:

To conduct this work, required data has been collected from the website of DOAJ available at <https://doaj.org/> (as on 24th December 2020). To retrieve the journals and their further details, filters were applied for refining the results under the Science subjects including Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy and Mathematics. The preliminary observation reveals that there are 104 journals in Zoology, 218 journals in Chemistry, 111 journals in Botany, 139 journals in Geology, 242 Journals in Physics, 85 Journals in Microbiology, 38 Journals in Astronomy, 52 Journals in Physiology, 11 Journals in Anatomy and 544 Journals in Mathematics. Further analysis was carried out on these journals spanning 2003 to 2020 and the values were noted through careful investigation. For each science journal relevant metadata such as Country of publication, language, year added in DOAJ, Article Processing Charges (APC) of journals, and licence attributes were tabulated and analysed using spreadsheet software in order to achieve the objectives of the study. The abbreviations used in study are ZOO-Zoology, CHEM-Chemistry, BOT-Botany, GEO-Geology, PHYS-Physics, MICRO-Microbiology, ASTR-Astronomy, PHYLS-Physiology, ANAT-Anatomy and MATH-Mathematics.

4. Results and Discussion:

4.1 Science Journals Inclusion and Visibility in DOAJ:

Total Document	ZOO	CHEM	BOT	GEO	PHYS	MICRO	ASTR	PHYSL	ANAT	MATH	Total
JOURNALS	104	218	111	139	242	85	38	52	11	544	1544
ARTICLES	44758	217000	48227	47835	170734	79462	20304	25273	2817	148450	1599494

Table 1: Total No. of Journals/Documents in DOAJ of Journals in Science

Figure 2. Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 3. Articles strength in Science Journals in DOAJ

Table 1, Fig 2&3 above shows the number of documents in the DOAJ Journals in Science. According to the data shown in the above table, Mathematics has the maximum number of OA Journals indexed in DOAJ whereas Anatomy has a minimum number of DOAJ indexed journals. Physics is ranked 2nd followed by Chemistry, Geology, Botany, Zoology, Microbiology, Astronomy, and Physiology. It can also be noted that ranking on the basis of the total number of articles also varies. CHEM has maximum number of articles followed by PHYS, MATH, MICRO, BOT, GEO, ZOO, PHYSL, ASTR and ANAT.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation - Ungrouped Data

Statistic	Journals	Articles
Mean	154.4	80486
Biased Variance	21758.24	4748697049.2
Biased Standard Deviation	147.506745608464	68910.7905135328
Covariance	7848682.55555556	
Correlation	0.694928559393183	
Determination	0.482925702660285	
T-Test	2.73343454344097	
p-value (2 sided)	0.0257088852635379	
p-value (1 sided)	0.0128544426317689	
95% CI of Correlation	[0.116102254562524, 0.921400432897904]	
Degrees of Freedom	8	
Number of Observations	10	

Table 2. Correlation between DOAJ Science Journals and Articles

Figure 4. QQplot of Journals Vs Articles

Table 2 and figure 4 depicts a medium positive correlation ($r^2 = +0.48$). Thus, it can be inferred that the number of OA science journals indexed by DOAJ and the articles they produce (research output) is positively related to the strength of such correlation is moderate.

4.2 Country level Contribution:

Countries	Science Subjects										Total
	ZOO	CHEM	BOT	GEO	PHYS	MICR	ASTR	PHYSL	ANAT	MATH	
Argentina	4	-	5	3	4	-	-	1	-	4	21
Arminia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Algeria	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Australia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	4	5
Austria	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	2
Bangladesh	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	2
Belarus	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	3
Belgium	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	4	5
Brazil	9	7	10	9	8	4	1	1	-	27	76

Bulgaria	8	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	16
Bolivia	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Canada	1	2	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	3	9
Chile	1	1	-	1	1	-	-	1	-	2	7
China	1	1	2	3	5	-	2	2	-	4	20
Colombia	2	2	2	3	2	-	-	-	-	7	18
Costa Rica	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	3
Croatia	-	4	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	4	11
Cuba	-	1	2	1	2	-	-	-	-	1	7
Czechia	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	6	10
Denmark	-	-	-	2	3	-	-	-	-	-	5
Ecuador	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	3
Estonia	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2
Ethiopia	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Egypt	-	1	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	2	6
Finland	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	2	4
France	3	1	3	2	6	1	-	1	-	13	30
Germany	7	7	5	19	16	5	4	3	-	15	81
Georgia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Greece	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2
Hong Kong	1	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	1	5
Hungary	-	2	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	5
India	-	6	2	-	2	7	-	-	1	3	21
Indonesia	5	25	3	6	24	5	2	1	-	93	164
Iran	1	10	2	5	6	4	1	3	1	16	49
Iraq	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	5

Poland	7	12	5	9	4	-	3	2	-	40	82
Portugal	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
Romania	-	1	2	4	5	-	1	-	1	21	35
Russian Federation	1	7	4	6	8	2	1	-	-	20	49
Serbia	-	2	2	3	1	1	1	-	-	4	14
Slovenia	1	1	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	6
Slovakia	-	-	-	2	1	1	1			2	7
Saudi Arabia	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2
South Africa	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	3
Singapore	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	5	8
Spain	4	-	5	3	2	2	-	1	1	13	31
Sri Lanka	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Switzerland	1	27	2	4	22	6	3	1	2	21	89
Sweden	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Thailand	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Taiwan	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	2
Tunisia	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Turkey	1	2	2	1	-	2	2	-	-	11	21
Ukraine	4	8	4	3	11	-	3	-	-	17	50
United Kingdom	13	41	14	15	46	24	4	14	1	76	248
United States	2	9	6	7	24	8	1	4	-	35	96
Venezuela	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2
Total	99	217	110	140	242	85	37	52	11	542	1535

Table 3: Country wise distribution of Science Journals in DOAJ

Table 3 reflects country wise distribution of science Journals indexed in DOAJ. It is found that altogether there are 99 Journals of Zoology, 217 Journals of Chemistry, 110 Journals of Botany, 140 Journals of Geology, 242 Journals of Physics, 85 Journals of Microbiology, 37 Journals of Astronomy, 52 Journals of Physiology, 11 Journals of Anatomy and 542 Journals of Mathematics listed in DOAJ published from 82 countries of the world. On the basis of the total journals published in DOAJ of select Journals of Sciences, United Kingdom was the most productive country in terms of number of journals (248) followed by Indonesia (164), United States (96) and Switzerland (89).

4.3 Indian Science Journals in OAJ

Detail	Title of the journal	Publisher and place	Added in DOAJ	Periodicity
CHEMISTRY n=6	i. Biomedical research journal	Wolters Kluwer Medknow, India	24 th Nov 2020	Bi-annual
	ii. To chemistry journal	PURKH, India	3rd March 2020	Tri-annual
	iii. Indian journal of Biochemistry and bio physics	NISCAIR, India	31 st December 2019	Bimonthly
	iv. National journal of laboratory medicine	JCDR Research and Publications pvt. ltd India	3 rd October 2016	Quarterly
	v. Indian Journal of Advances in chemical science	KROS, India	20th July 2016	Quarterly
	vi. Journal of pharmacy and Bio allied sciences	Wolters Kluwer Medknow, India	11th December 2009	Quarterly
BOTANY n=2	vii. Tropical plant research	Society for tropical plant research, India	15 th March 2018	Tri-annual
	viii. Indian journal of natural products and resources	NISCAIR, India	21st August 2017	Quarterly
PHYSICS n= 2	ix. Radiation protection and environment	Wolters Kluwer Medknow, India	18th May 2018	Quarterly

	x. International journal of advances in applied mathematics and mechanics	International journal of advances in applied mathematics and mechanics, India	9th March 2016	Quarterly
MICROBIOLOGY n=7	xi. Biomedical research journal	Wolters Kluwer Medknow , India	24th November 2020	Quarterly
	xii. Journal of pure and applied microbiology	Journal of pure and applied microbiology, India	2 nd November 2019	Quarterly
	xiii. Indian journal of pathology and microbiology	Wolters Kluwer Medknow , India	28th February 2018	Quarterly
	xiv. International journal of mycobacteriology	Wolters Kluwer Medknow, India	9th November 2016	Quarterly
	xv. National journal of laboratory medicine	JCDR Research and Publications pvt.ltd, India	3rd October 2016	Quarterly
	xvi. Journal of advanced laboratory research in biology	Society of open science, India	3rd April 2013	Quarterly
	xvii. Indian journal of medical microbiology	Wolters Kluwer Medknow, India	20th January 2004	Quarterly
ANATOMY n=1	xviii. National journal of clinical anatomy	Wolters Kluwer Medknow, India	26th May 2020	Quarterly
MATHEMATICS n=3	xix. International journal of mathematics engineering and management sciences	International journal of mathematics engineering and management sciences, India	18th September 2019	Bimonthly
	xx. International journal of advances in applied mathematics and mechanics	International journal of advances in applied mathematics and mechanics, India	9th March 2016	Two issues per year.

	xxi. International journal of cyber criminology	International journal of cyber criminology	8th May 2008	Bi-annual
Total	21 Indian Journals			

Table 4: Indian contribution of Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 5 Indian Science Journals in DOAJ

Table 4 reflects the Indian science Journals indexed in DOAJ. The data extracted from DOAJ reveal that there are 6 Journals in Chemistry, 2 Journals in Botany, 2 Journals in Physics, 7 Journals in Microbiology, 1 Journals in Anatomy and 3 Journals in Mathematics, whereas Zoology, Geology, Astronomy and Physiology have not an even single Journal is indexed in DOAJ.

4.4 Scholarly Communication Language:

Language											
	ZOO	CHEM	BOT	GEO	PHYS	MICR	ASTR	PHYLS	ANAT	MATH	Total
Arabic	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	3
Belarusian	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	2

Bulgarian	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2
Bosnian	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	1
Catalan	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Chinese	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	3
Croatian	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	4
Czech	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	3
Dutch	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
English	95	199	104	121	216	77	36	47	11	449	1355
Finnish	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
French	5	3	3	7	-	2	-	1	-	15	36
German	4	2	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	3	12
Indonesian	3	22	2	3	23	4	1	1	-	77	136
Italian	5	-	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	4	12
Japanese	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	2
Korean	-	1	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	4
Kazakh	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Lithuanian	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
Norwegian	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Persian	-	-	1	5	3	3	-	2	-	1	15
Polish	-	2	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	2	6
Portuguese	6	7	13	6	7	-	1	2	-	30	72
Romanian	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Russian	4	14	7	10	13	2	2	-	-	30	82
Serbian	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	-	3
Serbo-Croatian	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1
Slovak	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	1	5

Slovenian	2	-	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	5
Spanish	20	9	21	12	11	1	-	3	-	33	110
Turkish	1	1	2	-	-	2	1	-	-	1	8
Ukrainian	3	6	4	3	9	-	2	-	-	14	41
Total	156	270	161	179	287	95	47	60	11	668	1934

Table 5: Language assessment of Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 6 Scholarly communication language in DOAJ Science Articles

Language is the vital mode of communication and any scholarly publication requires a language to be published for its target audience. Table 4 reflects the language assessment of the open access Science Journals. It is reflected that the Science Journals indexed in DOAJ are published in 32 languages out of which English is the predominant language. English is the standard language of scholarly Journals. One thousand three hundred fifty-five journals are published in English. The second dominant language is Indonesian with 136 Journals followed by Spanish with 110 Journals, Russian (82), Portuguese (72) and French (36) and so on. Fig. 6 clearly indicates that English is the preferred language in scholarly communication via Science journals (70%) while all other non-English combined has only 30% representation.

4.5 Creative Commons (CC) Licenses:

Licensing Attribution											
	ZOO	CHEM	BOT	GEOT	PHYS	MICRO	ASTR	PHYSL	ANAT	MATH	Total

CC BY	51	130	53	74	153	47	16	24	4	278	830
CC BY-NC-ND	23	39	22	27	40	15	14	12	2	91	285
CC BY-NC	20	26	15	18	28	13	4	9	2	59	194
CC BY-NC-SA	3	12	10	10	4	7	-	6	1	33	86
CC BY-SA	5	12	4	9	8	2	4	1	-	56	101
CC BY-ND	-	-	-	-	6	-	-	-	-	10	16
Publisher's own license	2	4	8	2	8	3	-	1	2	17	47

Table 6: Licensing of Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 7 Application of CC licences by DOAJ Science journals

CC-BY (Attribution) this licence lets others distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the work, even commercially, as long as they credit the for the original creation. CC-BY is the most accommodating of licences offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licenced materials (Kumar 2018,174-179). CC-BY-NC-ND (Attribution-Non-Commercial-No Derives) this licence is the most restrictive of the six main licences, only allowing others to download the works and share them with others as long as they credit the work, but they can't change them in any way or use them commercially. CC-BY-NC (Attribution-Non-Commercial) this licence lets others remix, adapt, and build upon the work non-commercially, and although

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4.6 Growth Trends

Year											
	ZOO	CHEM	BOT	GE O	PHYS	MICRO	ASTR	PHYLS	ANAT	MATH	TOTAL
2020	12	37	10	19	34	14	7	11	1	75	220
2019	7	31	14	15	33	10	3	10	-	62	185
2018	10	22	10	16	36	10	5	4	1	67	181
2017	8	30	14	21	34	5	3	5	2	85	207
2016	5	18	14	17	24	9	3	3	2	55	150
2015	11	19	8	13	20	3	8	3	1	45	131
2014	2	5	1	3	5	1	-	1	-	10	28
2013	5	11	8	3	5	8	1	3	1	39	84
2012	5	8	4	3	6	5	1	1	-	14	47
2011	7	10	4	7	10	4	-	4	-	9	55

1											
2010	5	4	6	4	7	4	-	1	1	26	58
2009	3	6	2	2	5	2	1	1	-	10	32
2008	5	5	4	3	3	2	2	1	1	13	39
2007	2	1	1	5	6	-	-	-	-	9	24
2006	4	1	3	3	1	-	1	1	-	10	24
2005	3	2	1	2	3	-	-	-	-	2	13
2004	8	2	4	3	3	4	1	-	1	3	29
2003	1	5	2	-	6	3	2	1	-	7	27
Total	103	217	110	139	241	84	38	50	11	541	1534

Table 7: Year-wise addition of Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 8a Growth Trend of DOAJ Science journals (2003-2020)

Figure 8b Growth Trend of DOAJ Science journals (2003-2020)

Table 7 indicates that DOAJ started functioning in 2003 when there were only 1 Zoology Journal, 5 Journal of Chemistry and so on and then there has been a steady rise in the inclusion of Science Journals in open access domain and the number reached to 103, 217, 110, 139, 241, 84, 38, 50, 11 and 541, respectively, till 24 December 2020. 2020 can be marked as the most significant year as the highest number of (220) Journals have been added in DOAJ, 207 Journals were added in 2017, 185 Journals in 2019 and 181 Journals in 2018 (Sahoo, Mohanty, and Priyadarshini 2017, 1567).

4.7 APC Status:

APCs	With APC	Without APC
ZOOLOGY	36	68
CHEMISTRY	123	97
BOTANY	45	65
GEOLOGY	47	92
PHYSICS	141	101
MICROBIOLOGY	64	21

ASTRONOMY	14	24
PHYSIOLOGY	32	20
ANATOMY	8	3
MATHEMATICS	177	365
Total	687	856

Table 8: Article processing charges (APC) of Select Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 9 Status of APC in DOAJ Science journals (2003-2020)

Table 8 reports that the final published version of the article is permanently and freely available online for anyone, anywhere to read in Gold OA. Here, the publishers of the Journals charge some amount from the authors known as "Article Processing Charges" (APC) or handling charges. An Article-Publishing-Charge (APC) is usually applicable if published under Gold OA. Hybrid Open Access describes a publishing model where some articles are made openly available, against the payment of an Article Processing Charge (APC), while other articles remain closed access, and the journal as a whole subscription-based. When it comes to APC charges of Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy and Mathematics Journals in DOAJ, it is seen that 68, 97, 65, 92, 101, 21,

24, 20, 3, and 365 Journals respectively do not collect APC charges whereas only 36, 123, 45, 47, 141, 64, 14, 32, 08 and 177 (Sahoo, Birtia, and Mohanty 2017,116-119) Journals, respectively, accept APC charges from the authors.

4.8 DOAJ Seal

The DOAJ Seal is awarded to journals that demonstrate best practices in open access publishing. Around 10% of journals indexed in DOAJ have awarded the Seal. Journals do not need to meet the Seal criteria to be accepted into DOAJ. There exist seven criteria, which a journal must meet to be eligible for the DOAJ Seal. Table below presents the status of DOAJ Science journals in context-with DOAJ seal (“Directory of Open Access Journals,” n.d.)

DOAJ Seal	Yes	No
ZOOLOGY	14	90
CHEMISTRY	48	170
BOTANY	12	98
GEOLOGY	32	107
PHYSICS	57	185
MICROBIOLOGY	22	63
ASTRONOMY	7	31
PHYSIOLOGY	10	42
ANATOMY	2	9
MATHEMATICS	77	465
Total	281	1260

Table 9 & Figure 10: DOAJ Seal of Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 11. DOAJ Seal of Science Journals in DOAJ

The DOAJ Seal is a mark of certification for open access journals, awarded by DOAJ to Journals that achieve a high level of openness, adhere to Best Practice and high publishing standards (Mehraj and Ganaie 2019,2728). Table 8 reveals that 90, 170, 98, 107, 185, 63, 31, 42, 09 and 465 journals of Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy and Mathematics do not have DOAJ Seal, whereas only 14, 48, 12, 32, 57, 22, 7, 10, 02, and 77 Journals, respectively, have a Certification of DOAJ Seal. Fig. 10 depicts that 82% of the DOAJ Science journals are without DOAJ Seal whereas only 18% of these journals meet the criteria of DOAJ Seal. Fig. 11 displays the breakup of the DOAJ Science journals with reference to fulfilment of DOAJ Seal criteria.

4.9 PEER REVIEW

Peer Review											Total
	ZOO	CHEM	BOT	GEO	PHYS	MICR	ASTR	PHYL	ANAT	MATH	
Double blind peer review	20	43	30	31	39	25	11	13	3	162	377
Peer review	41	42	33	51	68	13	9	14	3	104	378

Blind peer review	43	133	47	56	128	47	17	25	5	272	773
Editorial review	-	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	-	1	4
Open peer review	-	1	-	1	7	-	-	-	-	4	13
Total	104	218	111	139	243	85	38	52	11	544	1545

Table 10: Peer Review of Select Social Science Journals in DOAJ

Figure 12a Peer-Review System in DOAJ Science Journals

Peer review is the evaluation of work by one or more people with similar competencies as the producers of the work (Kumar 2018,174-179). DOAJ journals deploys different types of peer review system. There are 773 Journals which are Blind peer review followed by 378 Journals and 377 journals which are peer review and double-blind peer review respectively. Only 13 Journals are Open peer review and 4 journals are editorial review.

Table 9 shows that Peer review is the evaluation of work by one or more people with similar competencies as the producers of the work. DOAJ used different types of peer-review. There are 773 Journals, which are Blind peer-review followed by 378 journals and 377 journals, which are peer-review and double-blind peer-review, respectively. Only 13 journals are Open peer-review and 4 journals are editorial review.

Figure 12b Peer-Review System in DOAJ Science Journals

Figure 12a and 12b reveals that blind peer-review (50%) the pre-dominant system of evaluating the quality of submitted manuscripts pre-publication followed by peer-review (25%), double blind peer-review (24%). It was found that open peer-review is still evolving in case of Science journals indexed by DOAJ.

5.0 Study Findings:

The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) contains an authoritative list of open access Journals in (Sahoo, Birtia, and Mohanty 2017,116-119) Science covering Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy, Mathematics. Mathematics has the maximum number of documents indexed in DOAJ whereas Anatomy has a minimum number of documents indexed in DOAJ. On the basis of the total journals published in DOAJ of Journals of Science United Kingdom is ranked 1st with 248 Journals followed by Indonesia (164), United States (96) and Switzerland (89) and so on. There are 6 Journals of Chemistry, 2 Journals of Botany, 2 Journals of Physics, 7 Journals of Microbiology, 1 Journal of Anatomy and 3 Journals of Mathematics indexed in DOAJ and Zoology, Geology, Astronomy and Physiology have not even single journal indexed in DOAJ till 24th December 2020. It is reflected that the Science Journals indexed in DOAJ are published in 32 languages out of which English is the predominant language. There are seven types of Creative Commons attribution given and out of these seven types, the highest number of Journals used CC-BY licencing i.e., 830. 2020 can be marked as the most significant year as the highest number of (220) Journals have been added in DOAJ, 207 Journals were added in 2017 and 185 Journals in 2019. The authors determine that APC charges of Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy and Mathematics Journals in DOAJ, it is seen that 68, 97, 65, 92, 101, 21, 24, 20, 3, and 365 Journals respectively do not collect APC charges whereas only 36, 123, 45, 47, 141, 64, 14, 32, 08 and 177 Journals, respectively, accept APC charges from the authors. The study reveals that 90, 170, 98, 107, 185, 63, 31, 42, 9 and 465 journals of Zoology, Chemistry, Botany, Geology, Physics, Microbiology, Astronomy, Physiology, Anatomy and Mathematics do not have DOAJ Seal, whereas only 14, 48, 12, 32, 57,

2, 7, 10, 2 and 77 Journals, respectively, have a Certification of DOAJ Seal and Maximum Journals (778) are blind peer-review.

6.0 Conclusion:

DOAJ keeps its position as the most comprehensive searchable database of free scientific and scholarly research in full-text formats. DOAJ is an authoritative choice for the scholarly community in need of immediate access to peer-reviewed content. The numbers of scholarly journals in Science have increased over the years (Sahoo, Birtia, and Mohanty 2017,116-119). For developing economies with academic and research libraries having less financial support for subscribing to premium content, the availability of 1544 journals in various Science disciplines potentially benefits academic stakeholders. The situation will be more fruitful, with the addition of more journals meeting the DOAJ criteria for inclusion. As far as contribution of Indian publishers is quite low as only 21 Indian Journals are available, although the number of journals offering free downloading of their articles are much more. These journals should convert to Libre Open Access and tweak their policies and procedures to meet the DOAJ inclusion criteria.

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